

Surgical Management of Irreducible Intussusception in Female “German Shepherd” Dog

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Abstract

A 1.5-year-old female German Shepherd was presented to VCC, College of Veterinary Science & A.H, Mhow with history of anorexia, vomiting and constipation. On the basis of history and abdominal radiograph Intussusception was diagnosed. End to End anastomosis was done to correct the condition. Postoperative antibiotics and analgesics were given and patient was kept on IV fluid for 5 days. Follow up was done until complete recovery, no major complications were noted and animal recovered uneventfully.

Keywords: Intussusception, end to end anastomosis, intussusceptions, German Shepherd.

Introduction

Intussusception is an invagination of a segment of gastrointestinal tract into the lumen of an adjoining segment which mainly arises due to any condition responsible for hyperperistalsis i.e., parasitism, enteritis, foreign bodies, previous surgical procedures etc (Fossum et al., 2019). Intussusception is recognized as a common cause of bowel obstruction in small animals (Levitt and Bauer., 1992).

History and diagnosis

A female German Shephard dog, age 18 months, body weight-20 kg was brought to

Veterinary Clinical Complex, College of Veterinary Science & AH, Mhow, with history of complete anorexia, vomiting, constipation and abdominal straining for past 20 days.

On the basis of history, clinical signs & lateral abdominal radiograph some obstruction near ileo-colic junction was diagnosed tentatively. End to End anastomosis after exploratory laparotomy under general anesthesia was done to correct the condition surgically.

Hemato-biochemical parameter (pre-operative)

S.no	Particular	Value	S.no	Particular	Value
1	Hb (g/dl)	9.5	8	Lymphocytes (%)	23
2	PCV (%)	30.9	9	Monocytes (%)	00
3	RBC 10 ⁶ /cu.mm	5.03	10	Eosinophils (%)	00
4	WBC (10 ³ /cu.mm)	13.2	11	Basophils (%)	00
5	Platelets (10 ³ /cu.mm)	108	12	BUN (mg/dl)	45.6
6	Neutrophils (%)	77	13	Creatinine(mg/dl)	1.3
7	SGPT (IU/L)	16.4	14	SGOT (IU/L)	83.4

Pre-operative management and Anesthesia

The entire abdomen and caudal thorax were clipped and site prepared aseptically using Savlon, Povidone Iodine and Isopropyl Alcohol.

Pre-operatively antibiotic coverage with Ampicillin @15mg/kg b.wt IV, Enrofloxacin @20mg/kg b.wt IV & inf .Metrogyl (metronidazole) 50 ml IV were given one hour before the surgery. Fluid therapy with Normal Saline & Ringers Lactate was maintained throughout the surgical process by intravenous route.

Anesthesia was given by combination of atropine @0.045mg/kg b.wt IM and xylazine @1mg/kg b.wt IM as premedication and butorphanol as analgesic @ 0.2mg/kg b.wt IV. Induction was done by Ketamine @ 5mg/kg b.wt IM and maintenance of anaesthesia was done by Diazepam and Ketamine (1:1) combination by IV route.

Surgical correction

The dog was positioned in dorsal recumbency and the abdomen was incised from xiphoid to pubis (Fig.2). The abdominal cavity is entered through an incision in linea alba.

Intussusceptum and intussusceptions were so tightly attached (Fig.1) that it was irreducible to normal anatomical position. The continuous lavaging was done with warm normal saline. The dilated intestine was transected at right angle and smaller segment at an oblique angle as intestinal segments were of disparate size (Fig.3). The end-to-end anastomosis was done with Vicryl 4-0 suture material using round bodied 20mm needle. Suture line is checked for leaks by milking intestinal contents across the anastomosis. The abdominal muscles and skin were closed using Vicryl no.0 suture material and Silk no 1 (Fig.4) suture material respectively.

Fig.1

Fig 2

Fig.3

Fig 3

Figure -5 (Resected part)

Post-operative management

Post operatively; Pantaprazole @1mg/kg b.wt IV , Antibiotics: Ampicillin @ 20 mg/kg b.wt.bid IV and Enrofloxacin @ 20 mg/kg b.wt. IV bid were given for 5 days and analgesic buprenorphine @ 0.02 mg/kg OD IV for 3 days.

Owner was advised to apply an Elizabethan collar to prevent the licking or rubbing of the wound & to hold food for 5 days post operative and dog was kept on IV fluids – RL 250ml bid IV, D-25 250 ml bid IV and Metronidazole 30 ml bid IV for 5 days. Owner was advised to give around 100 ml coconut water daily PO for 5 days. Wound dressing was done on alternate day with Povidone Iodine 10% (Betadine) and Mupirocin (Staphban ointment) for 10 days. The skin sutures were removed on day 13th post-operation. The dog recovered uneventfully without any noticeable post-operative complications.

Conclusion and Discussion

In our case intussusceptum and intussusceptions were tightly attached that they can't be brought back to normal anatomic position so end to end anastomosis was done to correct the condition surgically, with no intra-operative and post-operative complications. Four months after the surgery the dog was doing well with no evidence of reoccurrence of intussusception.

Young animals are most often affected, especially after parvoviral enteritis (Fossum et al., 2019).

To ensure that the anastomosis is made with healthy tissue, at least a few millimeters of normal intestine is removed with the diseased portion (Slatter, 2003).

References

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